

Visual Map – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

Visual map of the theory, the ambit of the main two equations and the range of phenomena that is under its power of reasoning and prediction. Some things are not mentioned due to lack of ability to put the complexity of the situation on the graph – such as family series equation.

Introduction

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)